

Standard Operating Protocol for the Measurement of Color in Intact Cooked Potatoes Using the DigiEye

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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SOP: Measurement of Color in Intact Cooked Potatoes Using the DigiEye

Date: 01/05/2024

Release: 1

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ABSTRACT

Potato varieties have diverse biophysical characteristics, so it is important for breeders to have the capacity to choose those that meet end users' preferences. Combining users' preferences with descriptive information about the sensory characteristics of boiled potato can contribute to the improvement of consumer-driven varieties. Boiled potato acceptance traits such as color can be integrated in the potato breeding program/product profile. Color can easily be quickly and directly measured by the DigiEye (DigiEye System, VeriVide Ltd., Leicester, UK). The SOP highlights the procedure of DigiEye image color prediction in intact cooked potato.

Key Words: Image analysis, Color, Potato, DigiEye

1 SCOPE AND APPLICATION

1.1 References

Nantongo SJ, Serunkuma E, Burgos G, Devrieux Fabrice, K M, Reuben S (2022) SOP for near infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) acquisition on sweetpotato roots and potato tubers. WP3.

Nakatumba-Nabende Joyce, Katumba Andrew, Murindanyi Sudi, Nabiryo Ann Lisa, Babirye Claire, Tusubira Jeremy Francis, Mutegeki Henry, Nantongo Judith Ssali, Sserunkuma Edwin, Ssali Reuben, Meghar Karima, Davrieux Fabrice. 2023. Standard operating procedure for image capture in sweetpotato and potato, and sensory attribute prediction. Work package 3. Kampala: RTBfoods Project-CIRAD, 18 p. <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00721>

Nakitto, M., Johanningsmeier, S.D., Moyo, M., Bugaud, C., de Kock, H., Dahdouh, L., Forestier-Chiron, N., Ricci, J., Khakasa, E., Ssali, R.T. and Mestres, C., 2022. Sensory guided selection criteria for breeding consumer-preferred sweetpotatoes in Uganda. *Food Quality and Preference*, 101, p.104628.

1.2 Definitions

Potato sensory quality comprises several attributes or characteristics included in appearance, texture, and taste and odor or aroma, all of them particularly important in terms of consumer satisfaction, determining both first purchase and repeated purchases.

1.3 Principle

DigiProduction is a 64-bit modular computer controlled digital imaging system for measuring colour and capturing high quality repeatable images. DigiProduction (DigiEye) can display both colours and texture of surfaces.

1.4 Reagents

Distilled water is required for cleaning the samples

1.5 Apparatus

Apparatus for sample preparation. These include knives for peeling, water for washing, towels for patting the samples dry and chopping board.

The DigiProduction - DigiGrade system. This consists of an illumination cabinet, digital camera and desktop personal computer running Windows operating system with a colour monitor. The details are documented in a different SOP <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00721>.

2 PROCEDURE

2.1 Ex: Extraction

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Sample preparation

Images were taken from both raw-intact and cooked-intact potato tubers. Sample selection and preparation is detailed in the NIRS SOP, DOI:10.18167/agritrop/00708. The images were taken along the cross-section of raw or cooked peeled samples.

Image collection

The process of image collection was documented earlier. Briefly, the images are captured as raw peeled or cooked inside the illumination cabinet that controls the amount of light that reaches the sample. The images are stored on an attached monitor. The description of the DigiEye calibration and general function is described in a different SOP (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00721>).

Figure 1: DigiEye images of a replicated (a) raw and (b) cooked potato sample

Color metrics

The color of the captured image is directly provided by the DigiEye. The color is presented in the LABCH color scheme, where L* indicates lightness, A* is the red/green coordinate, B* is the yellow/blue coordinate, C* represents chroma, and H is the hue angle. However, other statistics such as mean and variance of pixels can be derived. These metrics are directly downloadable in a spreadsheet for downstream analyses.

2.2 Ex: Solution of the standards of sugars & organic acids

NA.

2.3 Ex: Chromatographic conditions

NA

3 EXPRESSION OF RESULTS

3.1 Method of calculation and formulae

3.1.1 Calculation

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Calculation of correlations between DigiEye image color metrics and sensory panel correlations provides an equation for future direct prediction of cooked potato color without the use of the sensory panel. In the cooked samples, the yellow color of potato was more linearly associated with C (chroma) with an R2= 0.80. This model is sufficient for color selections in breeding programmes.

3.1.2 Formulae

The linear equation is given by;

$$y=6.8345x-6.8172$$

Where y= is the DigiEye C measurement and X is the sensory predicted color.

3.2 Repeatability

Repeatability assessed from 5 measurements of the same sample by the same analyst indicated a deviation of ±2 units for the L color values.

4 CRITICAL POINTS OR NOTE ON THE PROCEDURE

The important points to note while estimating color are related to the proper handling and operation of the DigiEye, and these are listed in a published SOP (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00721>).

The samples should also be scanned in the shortest time possible after cross-sectioning to reduce oxidation that affects color.

5 TEST REPORT

The highest correlations between the sensory and DigiEye LABCH color scales in cooked potato samples are indicated below (Table 1), where L represents brightness; for A, negative values refer to greenish and positive values refer to red; for B, negative values refer to blue and positive values refer to yellow; C* stands for saturation; and H° stands for Hue.

Table 1: correlations between the sensory and DigiEye LABCH color scales in cooked potato

	Yellow color
L	-0.26
A	0.63
B	0.87
C	0.87
H	-0.76

APPENDICES

5.1 Annex 1: LABCH color values of cooked potato measured by the digieye

sample	l	a	b	c	h
C395.171 C1	75.38	-2.7	33.42	33.53	94.62
C395.171 C2	74.56	-2.54	32.6	32.7	94.45
C395.171 C3	71.34	1.7	39.8	39.83	87.55
C301023.15 C1	81.4	-2.94	19.87	20.09	98.4
C301023.15 C2	79.97	-1.21	26.64	26.67	92.6
C301023.15 C3	79.53	-2.58	21.56	21.72	96.82
C301044.36 C1	75.42	-0.05	38.1	38.1	90.07
C301044.36 C2	75.69	0.28	41.65	41.65	89.61
C301044.36 C3	73.38	1.14	43.75	43.77	88.5
C304351.5 C1	75.34	1.66	40.05	40.08	87.63
C304351.5 C2	71.51	1.16	35.12	35.14	88.11
C304351.5 C3	74.87	1.09	34.97	34.99	88.22
C304366.46 C1	79.4	1.11	44.03	44.05	88.56
C304366.46 C2	78.99	1.26	45.21	45.23	88.4
C304366.46 C3	80.61	1.47	44.22	44.25	88.1
C304383.41 C1	81.15	-0.91	22.21	22.23	92.34
C304383.41 C2	76.86	-2.81	17.17	17.4	99.31
C304383.41 C3	76.2	-0.8	21.35	21.36	92.15
C398095.231C1	73.51	-0.21	33.7	33.7	90.35
C398095.231C2	76.9	2.06	41.5	41.55	87.16
C398095.231C3	75	2.49	43.54	43.61	86.73
C397014.2C1	81.45	-2.1	15.15	15.3	97.89
C397014.2C2	80.68	-2.1	15.04	15.18	97.95
C397014.2C3	74.56	-2.4	12.66	12.89	100.75
C398208.68C1	78.29	-1.22	29.74	29.76	92.36
C398208.6C2	80.29	-0.94	32.65	32.66	91.65
C398208.68C3	77.76	-0.88	31.15	31.16	91.61
DUTCH C1	74.14	0.49	33.72	33.73	89.17
DUTCH C2					
DUTCH C3	73.67	1.14	36.27	36.28	88.2
KACHPOT C1	73.69	2.67	42.33	42.42	86.39
KACHPOT C2	71.44	1.94	39.38	39.42	87.18
KACHPOT C3	71.64	2.9	43.34	43.44	86.17
KINIGI C1	70.66	1.33	34.16	34.19	87.77
KINIGI C2	73.16	-0.32	35.51	35.51	90.51

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KINIGI C3	72.93	-0.51	34.7	34.71	90.84
N2016.15C1	75.12	0.46	40.86	40.86	89.36
N2016.15C2	76.01	1.08	42.29	42.31	88.53
N2016.15C3	75.2	1.82	40.99	41.03	87.45
N2016.19C1	77.24	-2.51	25.19	25.31	95.69
N2016.19C2	76.08	-3.27	19.55	19.83	99.5
N2016.19C3	81.5	-1.89	24.1	24.18	94.5
SHANGI C1	82.89	-0.44	34.74	34.74	90.72
SHANGI C2	84.44	-0.06	35.7	35.7	90.09
SHANGI C3	83.2	0.05	35.07	35.07	89.92
UNICA C1	76.88	-0.33	36.7	36.7	90.51
UNICA C2	71.73	0.09	39.18	39.18	89.87
UNICA C3	75.68	-0.79	34.69	34.7	91.31
WANJIKU C1	78.33	-1.99	26.34	26.42	94.32
WANJIKU C2	78.41	-3.75	20.29	20.63	100.47
WANJIKU C3	76.63	-1.67	22.71	22.77	94.21